

VARIETY OF SOCIAL NETWORKS AND THEIR ROLE IN STUDYING OF FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Abstract. The purpose of this article is to study the educational potential of social networks in the process of studying foreign languages. Considerable attention is paid to the variety of mobile applications and language sites for communication in the modern world. The article discusses the advantages of using these networks to solve a number of problems of teaching a foreign language.

Keywords: foreign language, social network, study of foreign languages, online learning.

Everyone learning a foreign language is known that the best way to master the language is immersion in the language environment and, accordingly, communication with its native speakers. But, unfortunately, the modern geopolitical situation in the world does not contribute to travel. However, the Internet gives us the opportunity to plunge into a foreign language environment without leaving home, visiting the linguistic exchange sites.

Language social networks favorably affect the motivation for the study of a foreign language, contribute to the growth of students' interest in this language. These sites were created specifically so that speakers of different languages could help each other in learning. It is no secret that the materials presented on these sites are often many times more interesting than those printed in our textbooks. Audiomaterials are relevant and repaired by native speakers. In addition, the variety of topics and problems for discussion helps to improve the ability to maintain dialogue and conduct discussions. All these factors accelerate the learning process, improve the quality of assimilation of the material and make language networks popular not only among young people, but also of the older generation.

Today on the Internet you can familiarize yourself with a huge number of various resources, choose the most suitable for yourself and learn the language, working on an individual program and at your pace.

One of these resources is the international Busu community. Busu is an international educational project aimed at learning foreign languages. The project allows you to practice with real native speakers, study their culture,

make new acquaintances. In total, it has more than 80 million students-users. Online courses in 12 languages, including Chinese, Arabic and Japanese languages, which are almost impossible to meet in other language social networks, are available in web version and mobile application. The materials presented on the site contribute to the improvement of all speech skills: readings, letters, audit and speaking. Each lesson is devoted to a specific topic, the user is provided with a dictionary of the necessary words and expressions, a set of written exercises for consolidating the material covered, a test for testing knowledge and a mandatory dialogue with a native speaker of the language being studied. Students are redirected to each other, everyone can become a teacher and adviser to those who study his native language. Having received a job, “teachers” correct mistakes and help their “students” understand the language.

Most of the materials presented on the website are free. If you want to access the video tutorials, or you will need a serial about the course of the course, then this can be done by acquiring a premium account. In addition to the above languages, here you can learn English, Russian, French, Italian, German, Spanish, Turkish, Polish.

You should also pay attention to the My Language Exchange project. More than 3 million people are users of this social network. If you want to find a friend by correspondence and improve your foreign language, it is to this site that you should pay attention. This project presents 115 languages, including the main European and Asian, as well as a variety of language games and a library. Like any social network, it provides an opportunity to exchange text messages, as well as agree on communication through Skype.

Duolingo.com - a free international language network was launched in 2011. The training system is built in the form of interesting lessons using the elements of the game, as the students help to translate websites, articles, etc.

In addition to the Duolingo web project, it has a mobile application. Not only the most popular European languages, such as English, German and French, but also Spanish, are presented to Duolino. Next year, it is planned to launch courses of the Swedish language. Currently, the Duolingo program is widely used by school teachers, since excellent exercises are presented here, aimed at the formation and improvement of listening and translation skills. This project motivates the regularity of classes (daily reminders come to the mail), and you can independently set the rhythm.

Lang8, Ling, Livemocha, Interpals, Lingualeo are sites that help learn foreign languages that everyone has to be heard. However, there are still a huge number of little -known, but by no means no less useful social networks and applications.

Babbel.com - a social network founded in 2008 in Germany to learn foreign languages provides an opportunity to study 14 languages. The target audience is listeners with the level of intermediate language and beginners. In addition, there is an opportunity to improve their knowledge of a foreign language in the field of marketing, advertising and PR, etc. Each course consists of short lessons, which, in turn, contain new words and phrases, exercises for their memorization and training of grammar. The repetition manager helps you work out lexical skills. A mobile application is actively used, it is possible to work off-line [1].

ES.COEFFEE.com is an interesting site for language exchange and language games. This site offers several language games that you can play on the network. For example, "Word Explainer" (the purpose of the game is to guess the words according to the description of other participants and offer a description of your words), "Make a Phrase" (the goal is to make the right phrase or phrase from the proposed words). The site presents 183 languages.

Verbling is an online resource that provides students with the opportunity to find tutors for online classes. Lessons are carried out individually in small groups, a maximum of 9 people. The choice of a teacher (necessarily a native speaker) is provided to the student. Having read information about the teacher and students' reviews, you can book a trial lesson and test your knowledge.

All classes are conducted through the Google Hangout application. In the lesson, work can be carried out both over pronunciation, vocabulary or grammar, as well as audit, speaking or writing.

Conversationexchange.com - thanks to this resource, you will have a great opportunity to chat with other users in chat, improve the level of ownership of a foreign language, and, among other things, get acquainted with the country's culture of the language being studied. Depending on what skills you prefer to develop and improve, your communication can occur both in the form of correspondence and "live communication" using Skype. More confident in their knowledge of listeners, this language platform provides an opportunity to learn about native speakers who live in your city and are ready to talk live in a public place. However, one should not forget that according to the rules of this social network, your communication should be "interchange", that is, you are both a

student and a teacher, helping your interlocutor in mastering a new foreign language for him.

The number of Internet resources devoted to the study of foreign languages is great and it is constantly growing. Most sites are designed for people who have mastered the initial level of language and want to practice in “living” communication with a person for whom this language is a native. Such social networks are an excellent help in the educational process, while the teacher can only organize the work of their students in the lesson, or outside of the school time. The use of language social networks in the study of a foreign language helps to diversify the learning process, make it interesting and exciting. Thus, we can conclude that language social networks are an effective method of teaching a foreign language.

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